

Stützenstumpverschweißung

Detail Dampfablassventil

Detail Temperaturhülse

Blindflansch Pos.1

Detail Berstscheibe

Detail Manometer/Überdruckventil

Manometer/Überdruckventil

Dampfablassventil

Thermometer

Berstscheibe

1. Technical data	shell side	tube side
Max. liquid column [m]	-	-
medium	Fäkalien	
Density (liquid / gaseous), max.	1000 kg/m ³	
Fluid group according to PED 2014/68 / EU	1 / flüssig	
volume ca. V [l]	2	
calculation Over pressure PS [bar]	+25	
calculation temperature TS [°C]	-10 / +200	
Test pressure standing / lying. PT [bar]	+39,25	
design rule	: EN 13445	
testing basis	: EN 13445, DGRL 2014/68/EU	
empty weight	: 20 kg	

customer ZHAW	scale: 1:5
	Fabr. No.: B-1733
	Low-Cost-Reaktor BLR
	Order number.: 21001.6
	Drawing No.: 21001.6
Zust. modification date name Origin:	Replacement for: Replacement by: